

The Effect of Alcohol on Sleep

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Abstract

Alcohol use is often used as a sedative and administered as a self-treatment for sleep disorders. Acute moderate use may reduce sleep onset latency, but accumulating evidence suggests that alcohol does indeed cause significant disruption of normal sleep architecture. This review discusses the acute and chronic effects of alcohol on sleep physiology and sleep quality. Acutely, alcohol shortens sleep onset latency and promotes first-half-of-the-night slow-wave sleep while suppressing REM sleep and increasing sleep fragmentation throughout the second half of the night as blood alcohol levels decrease. Chronic and heavy intake accentuates insomnia, frequent awakenings, decreased sleep efficiency, and long-term circadian disruption. These effects are mediated by alcohol-induced changes in major neurotransmitter systems, including GABA, glutamate, serotonin, norepinephrine, and acetylcholine, which play a crucial role in regulating sleep-wake functions. High rates of insomnia among individuals with alcohol use disorders reflect the complex interrelationship between alcohol and sleep disturbance. Overall, alcohol should not be considered a therapeutic sleep aid but rather a substantial disruptor of restorative sleep.

Keywords : Alcohol, Sleep, Acute effect, Prolonged Effect, Memory, Learning

Introduction

Alcohol refers to a category of organic compounds that are defined by the presence of one or more hydroxyl (—OH) groups bonded to a carbon atom within an alkyl group (hydrocarbon chain). These compounds can be viewed as organic variations of water (H_2O) where one of the hydrogen atoms has been substituted with an alkyl group, which is usually denoted by R in organic chemistry. For instance, in ethanol (commonly known as ethyl alcohol), the alkyl group present is the ethyl group, $\text{—CH}_2\text{CH}_3$ (Noller et al.2025). While excessive drinking can accelerate the start of many diseases and raise the risk of death, moderate alcohol use is known to lower the risk of death (Camargo et al., 1997, Russel et al., 2009). A

variety of neurological system issues, such as memory impairments, motor abnormalities, peripheral neuropathy, and diminished learning capacity, are also brought on by excessive drinking (Min 2009, Cloninger et al., 2009). As of 2012, 21.8% of Korean adult males were high-risk drinkers (average alcohol consumption of 7+ drinks on 2+ days per week). For individuals between the ages of 30 and 59, the high-risk drinking rate is more than 25%, suggesting that a sizable portion of the population is at risk from alcohol-related risks. Conversely, it has been claimed that 6.0% of women drink excessively (Ryu et al., 2013). Alcohol is a psychoactive substance that can be easily accessed given it is engrained in many social and cultural contexts (Rehm et al., 2009).

Sleep is the ultimate state which facilitate recovery from physical, mental and brain fatigue caused by the work done in the daytime and the other activities. It enables the human body to have the rest time for the learning, memory, preservation of the energy, development, recovery and growth also. It is a typical, reversible, recurring state characterized by decreased responsiveness to outside stimuli, accompanied by complex and predictable physiological changes. These changes involve coordinated and spontaneous brain activity generated internally, along with variations in hormone levels and muscle relaxation. A number of recent sleep studies have shown that inadequate sleep causes mood disorders, increased stress, and exhaustion but also increases the risk of cardiovascular disease, metabolic syndrome, and obesity. On the other hand, a lot of illnesses also impact the quality of sleep. Sleep difficulties have been linked to depression, anxiety, musculoskeletal conditions, obesity, restless legs syndrome, and other long-term illnesses. While a clearly defined specific function of sleep is still uncertain, this is partly because sleep is a dynamic state influencing all aspects of physiology, rather than a single organ or isolated physical system (Chang et al., 2014, Kenney et al., 2014, Young et al., 2002, Aldrich and Shipley, 1993, Yoon, 2013). Sleep fundamentally differs from wakefulness, during which there is an increased capacity for sensitivity and an effective response to external stimuli. The transition between sleep and wakefulness is the most prominent example in higher vertebrates of the broader concept of periodicity in the activity or responsiveness of living tissues (Cartwright et al 2025).

Beverages containing alcohol or ethanol have psychoactive and sedative components, which lead to dependency-producing properties. It has always been part of customs, tradition and cultural beliefs with several health effects. Its sedative nature leads you to fall asleep faster and reduces fall asleep time, as much research confirms consuming alcohol boosts sleep initially.

Alcoholic beverages lead the body to relax and become drowsy after consuming them. Its soothing effects interrupt the regular sleep pattern and disrupt the signals of neurotransmitters which regularise sleep and wakefulness when it is metabolised and rapidly absorbed by the bloodstream. The issue is that, at least initially, you are more likely to experience slow-wave sleep, also known as “deep sleep”, and less REM sleep when you go to bed with alcohol in your system. Light sleep, the lightest stage of sleep, is likely to increase later in the night after your body has processed the alcohol (I.M Colrain et al.2014). Frequent awakenings and disturbed, poor-quality sleep may follow from this. Alcohol remits the muscles of the body,

which can lead to problems like snoring and could lead to disordered sleeping. Alcohol is diuretic in nature, but alcohol like beer significantly increases urine production in the body as compared to other alcoholic beverages, which leads to sleep breaks during the night for bathroom use, impacting the sleep pattern and quality of sleep. Quality of sleep often depends upon several factors like age, sex, body, etc., as well as the amount of alcohol consumption by a person (**Soon-Yeob Park et al. 2015**).

Several studies indicate that consuming alcohol temporarily boosts drowsiness but ultimately leads to frequent awakenings during the night and early morning. Alcohol consumption causes a biphasic reaction in relation to variations in blood alcohol content throughout time (**Martin et al., 1993**). When alcohol is consumed for the first time, the blood alcohol content rises along with sensations of relaxation and exhilaration. However, alcohol usually has a sedative effect and functions as a central nervous system depressant when blood alcohol content rises (**Holdstock & Wit, 1998**).

Individuals with alcohol use disorders often drink before bedtime to enhance their sleep experience. Many moderate drinkers also use alcohol before sleeping when they experience insomnia. Although it is thought that drinking habits are closely linked to sleep patterns, no definitive empirical correlation has been established so far, and research on the relationship between drinking habits and sleep quality is still ongoing.

Fundamentals and Physiology of Sleep

Sleep is a state of immobility that can be quickly reversed. It is marked by a significant decrease in sensory responsiveness (**Campbell & Tobler, 1984**). Another important feature of sleep is its regulation. After losing sleep, people tend to want it more, which leads to what's known as 'sleep rebound' (**Campbell & Tobler, 1984**).

Sleep is not a single, uniform state; it exists on a continuum. The different components of the sleep continuum in mammals can be broadly divided into two main states: non-rapid eye movement (NREM) sleep and rapid eye movement (REM) sleep. Researchers use various electrophysiological measurements, such as electroencephalogram (EEG) to record brain activity, electrooculogram (EOG) to track eye movements, and electromyogram (EMG) to measure muscle activity, to objectively identify the different stages of the sleep-wake cycle (**Datta & Maclean, 2007**).

Active wakefulness is characterized by low-voltage, high-frequency EEG activity (greater than 15 Hz), REMs observed in EOG, and notable EMG activity. In human NREM sleep, there are three distinct stages: Stage I demonstrates low-voltage, mixed-frequency EEG patterns; Stage II features slow waves along with sleep spindles and K-complexes; and Stage III, known as slow-wave sleep, is distinguished by high-amplitude, low-frequency EEG signals. In laboratory animals, NREM sleep does not display these subdivisions and instead presents high-amplitude, low-frequency EEG waves. REM sleep is recognized by low-amplitude, high-frequency EEG activities, muscle atonia, rapid eye movements, and additional physiological indicators such as PGO activity, hippocampal theta activity, myoclonic twitches, and various cardio-respiratory

rhythms. Sleep in adult humans and non-human primates is generally monophasic, with NREM sleep predominating during the first half and REM sleep occurring in the latter half (**Thakkar et al. 2015**). It is estimated that 20–40 % of the global population fail to meet the current recommendations of seven to 9 h of sleep per night too (**Ohayon, 2011, Adams et al., 2016**).

Acute Effects of Alcohol on Sleep

Alcohol is commonly consumed prior to bedtime with the belief that it facilitates sleep (**Gardnier et al., 2024**). **Yules et al. (1966, 1967)** subsequent studies examined the impact of alcohol on sleep cycles for young men, focusing on REM and slow wave sleep (SWS). Early studies faced some challenges due to the lack of standard sleep scoring at the time, but were still able to find trends such as REM suppression and increased SWS. Further data were provided by **Rundell et al. (1972)** and **Prinz et al. (1980)**, identifying increased SWS on the first night of drinking, with inconsistent outcomes on subsequent nights. More specifically, **Feige et al. (2006)** demonstrated a significant decrease in REM density associated with high BAC levels, although reductions in percentage REM sleep have not been as consistently reported. Thus, although there is evidence supporting that alcohol affects REM sleep, further research will help confirm exactly how these effects endure across consecutive nights of drinking. Despite the potential to reduce sleep onset latency, alcohol may disrupt the maintenance of subsequent sleep (**Roehra & Roth, 2001**).

Prolong Effect of Alcohol on Sleep

The blood alcohol concentration depends on several factors, including gender, body weight, number of drinks, and individual metabolic rate, which generally ranges between 0.01 to 0.02 g% per hour (**Arnedt et al., 2011**). The dissimilarities in alcohol effects on sleep depend on peak levels in the first half of the night and its decline in the latter half. In general, moderate intake of alcohol (< 1 g/Kg) always shows a reduction of the duration of REM sleep (**Williams et al., 1983; Miyata et al., 2004; Roehrs et al., 1991**), with significant effects on second-half-of-the-night REM sleep (**Rundell et al., 1972; Miyata et al., 2004**). A key study by **Arnedt et al., 2011** showed that heavy intake (> 1 g/Kg) compared with a placebo resulted in increased SOL, decreased SE, and increased WASO. The consumption of alcohol increased the SWS%, stage 2, and REM latency while decreasing total REM%. During the first half of the night, heavy drinking increased the TST and improved sleep efficiency, while during the latter half, it reduced TST and increased awakenings (**Arnedt et al., 2011b**). In late adolescence, studies found sleep disruption with increased frontal delta and alpha activities after the use of alcohol (**Chan et al., 2013; Chan et al., 2015**). Additionally, early-evening consumption of alcohol, despite minimal breath alcohol level, resulted in subjective shallow sleep and increased high-frequency EEG activities, indicating increased arousal during sleep (**Landolt et al., 1996**). These findings suggest that moderate alcohol intake may lead to a reduction in REM sleep, while heavy intake initially may enhance sleep continuity and later result in sleep fragmentation as the night advances, and these changes may persist even when the breath alcohol concentration drops to undetectable levels.

Insomnia or disturbances in sleep are commonly observed in individuals with alcohol dependence. Estimates of prevalence range from 36% to 91% (**Mello and Mendelson, 1970, Brower et al., 2001b, Chaudhary et al., 2015, Baekeland et al., 1974, Cohn et al., 2003**). Alcohol dependence can be categorized into various stages based on the timing of alcohol exposure.

Alcohol and Sleep Disorders

Neurotransmitters are essential in determining how alcohol affects sleep in individuals with alcohol use disorders, as they aid in transmitting signals between neurons. These substances are secreted by one neuron, travel across the synapse, and attach to receptors on neighbouring neurons, thereby affecting signal generation and the production of proteins. Neurotransmitters can be classified as either stimulatory or inhibitory, depending on their influence on the generation of nerve signals. While research on the neurobiological effects of long-term alcohol use on sleep is somewhat limited (**Ehlers 2000**), there is considerable knowledge regarding the neurobiology of addiction (**Koob and Roberts 1999; Valenzuela and Harris 1997**) and **sleep patterns (Aldrich 1999; Jones 2000)**. The neurobiological pathways that affect sleep and are modified by alcohol provide a foundation for exploring their interrelated dynamics.

Early theories about the neurobiology of sleep emphasized the importance of monoamine neurotransmitters, specifically serotonin and norepinephrine (**Jouvet 1969**). Researchers suggested that alcohol interferes with sleep by impacting these neurotransmitters (**Johnson et al. 1970; Smith et al. 1971; Zarcone et al. 1978**). One study showed that disturbances in sleep related to alcohol consumption improved with the use of 5-hydroxytryptophan, which boosts serotonin levels (**Zarcone 1978**). On the other hand, research conducted by **Asheychik et al. (1989)** reported no enhancement in sleep with L-tryptophan among detoxified alcoholics, potentially due to their already good sleep patterns. The notion that low serotonin levels are the sole cause of poor sleep in alcoholics is dubious. Evidence indicates that activation of serotonin is not essential for normal sleep (**Jones 2000**). Important observations include: serotonin neurons in the raphe nucleus exhibit heightened activity during wakefulness, serotonin concentrations decrease during sleep, serotonin's effects can vary according to receptor types, ritanserin promotes slow-wave sleep (**Sharpley et al. 1994**), and normal sleep depends on various neurotransmitter systems and other factors influenced by alcohol.

The state of being awake is mainly controlled by the ascending reticular activating system along with several excitatory neurotransmitters, including norepinephrine, serotonin, dopamine, acetylcholine, histamine, and glutamate. Nonrapid eye movement (NREM) sleep, especially during slow-wave sleep (SWS), is marked by decreased excitatory activity and increased inhibitory neural processes supported by hypnogenic neurons in the basal forebrain and GABA-releasing neurons in the brain stem, which suppress the ascending reticular activating system (**Jones 2000**). In contrast, during REM sleep, the dynamics of neurotransmitters change, showing reduced activity in the monoamine and histamine systems, while acetylcholine and possibly glutamate become more active (**Aldrich 1999; Prospero-Garcia et al. 1994**).

The consumption of alcohol in acute phases significantly affects these neurotransmitter systems. Alcohol boosts GABA activity—an inhibitory neurotransmitter—while simultaneously inhibiting glutamate, which is excitatory. This combination contributes to the sedative effects of alcohol and its capability to suppress REM sleep (**Prospero-Garcia et al. 1994**). Moreover, alcohol reduces acetylcholine transmission (**Valenzuela and Harris 1997**). The importance of norepinephrine is also evident; mice that lack norepinephrine show increased sensitivity to the sedative effects of alcohol (**Weinshenker et al. 2000**), suggesting that norepinephrine may help counteract sedation (**Munoz et al. 1986**). Furthermore, selectively bred mice, including those with long-sleep and short-sleep phenotypes, exhibit different responses to alcohol's sedative effects, which are influenced by variations in baseline norepinephrine levels in their brain stems (**French et al. 1995**). Additionally, low doses of alcohol tend to be stimulating in humans and cause increased norepinephrine levels in rats, while higher doses reduce norepinephrine release, indicating a dose-dependent relationship with sleep initiation and duration in individuals consuming alcohol (**Roehrs and Roth 1995; Rossetti et al. 1992**). In the end, norepinephrine may significantly influence the disrupted sleep patterns seen after acute alcohol consumption, particularly among individuals with alcohol use disorders.

Methodology

Research literature, which are peer-reviewed article was searched online using databases such as PubMed, Google scholar and Science Direct as, well which investigates about the alcohols impact on sleep. Additional reference was discovered from the reference list of the important review paper.

Inclusion criteria

Article were included that satisfied the several criteria

- From peer-reviewed journals
- Affined with Alcohol fussing sleep quality, sleep stages (NREM/REM) and sleeping issues.
- Looked for short- and long-term exposure to alcohol

Exclusion criteria

- Primary focus was not on alcohol
- Unreliable and non-justifiable scientifically

Conclusion

As we've been doing some reading about the relationship between drinking and sleeping; clearly, there is a great deal more to alcohol's use as a "quick fix" for sleeping, than just its initial sedating effects caused by raising GABA levels (gamma amino/butyric acid) and lowering

glutamate levels. Thus, while the initial effects of alcohol may result in falling asleep faster; the drowsiness is short-lived and ultimately alcohol has a disruptive effect on the normal progression of sleep cycles. A full night of sound sleep is transformed into a series of poor-quality, interrupted sleep segments with no restorative value, leaving one groggy the following morning.

One of the most significant points from this study, is what researchers refer to as the “biphasic” effects of alcohol on the sleep cycle. While in the first part of the night you might achieve deep, slow-wave sleep; REM sleep is usually sacrificed during this period and since REM sleep is critical to emotional balance and cognitive functioning; the trade-off is significant. Further, in the second half of the night, after the body begins to metabolize the alcohol, you enter a “rebound arousal” period, characterized by frequent awakenings and transitions into a lighter stage of sleep where your heart rate increases and your muscles relax, resulting in increased snoring and/or sleep apnoea. For those who consume large quantities of alcohol on a regular basis; the repeated nighttime disruptions of sleep are not merely inconvenient; they contribute to chronic stress and create potential long-term health risks such as cardiovascular disease and metabolic syndrome.

Additionally, the neurobiological evidence also reveals a frightening pattern of dependence. When individuals use alcohol to “self-medicate” insomnia; the brain’s chemical messenger systems (i.e., norepinephrine and serotonin) become altered in ways that make it inherently more difficult to fall asleep. The result is a self-perpetuating cycle where an apparently corrective action for inadequate sleep becomes the principal cause. Significantly, as many as 91 percent of patients with alcohol use disorders also suffer from insomnia-an indication that alcohol severely impairs the body’s self-regulation processes responsible for sleep.

In conclusion, while alcohol may initially function as a strong sedative, it actually represents a significant disruptor to nocturnal sleep. Natural, restorative sleep is a balanced and dynamic process dependent on an appropriate interplay of neurotransmitters-an interaction significantly disrupted by alcohol. As empirical investigations further delineate these relationships, the public health implication is clear: the need to support improved sleep hygiene and to appreciate what is sacrificed by having a “nightcap.” interposing agent to the continuity of sleep required for recuperation It is therefore justifiable to update the literature concerning alcohol as a sleep promoter-to one that positions it as a major and development.

Conflict of Interests

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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